

Castor Oil based Polyurethane Anionomers

S. RAMESH and GANGA RADHAKRISHNAN*

Polymer Division, Central Leather Research Institute, Adyar, Madras-600 020

Manuscript received 1 April 1995, revised 29 December 1995, accepted 28 March 1996

Polyurethane ionomers are a special class of block copolymers used in a variety of fields¹. The presence of ionic groups in the polyurethane chain makes them water-dispersible or even water-soluble². The wide range of carboxyl, sulphonic and phosphoric acid groups containing diols available for the anionomer synthesis, lead these class of polymers into potential new fields of application with superior properties³. Castor oil has been used as polyol for the preparation of various types of polymers. Castor oil based polyurethanes have been used for numerous applications⁴.

We studied earlier⁵ the properties of polyurethane anionomers by performing addition reaction on the unsaturated site of the castor oil backbone. We report here the synthesis and characterisation of polyurethane anionomers (Scheme 1) based on castor oil and a linear aliphatic diol containing SO₃Na group.

Results and Discussion

The molecular weight data of the anionomers (Table 1) reveal reasonable molecular weight buildup in both the systems. The analysis was performed in the presence of an electrolyte LiBr to minimise the polymer-solvent interaction which would otherwise lead to changes in the shape of the elution curves leading to unusual molecular weight distributions. The broad dispersity obtained here was due to some amount of branching since castor oil has a functionality above two.

In the FTIR spectra of the polyurethane anionomer, the carbonyl of the ester group in the ricinolenic acid of the castor oil unit and the carbonyl of the urethane groups frequencies are merged as a broad signal at 1732 cm⁻¹. Band due to C-N stretching and N-H deformation is observed at

1541 cm⁻¹. The C=C stretching of the unsaturated group of the castor oil and that of the aromatic units of the TDI are observed at 1601 cm⁻¹. The urethane-NH stretching is observed around 3410 cm⁻¹. But the shortening of the bandwidth here when compared to polyether systems is due to the absence of more number of hydrogen bond interacting sites in the mainly hydrocarbon backbone of the castor oil units.

TABLE I

Polymer composition	Code	GPC data			<i>T_g</i> °C
		\bar{M}_n 10 ⁻⁴	\bar{M}_w 10 ⁻⁴	\bar{M}_w / \bar{M}_n	
Castor oil (1 mol)/ TDI (3 mol)/ionic diol (1 mol) + BD (1 mol)	C11	3.09	12.79	4.14	-42.0
Castor oil (1 mol)/ TDI (3 mol)/ionic diol (2 mol)	C12	2.98	11.74	3.94	-46.5

Thermal analysis : Fig. 1 shows the thermograms of the polyurethane anionomers. The multistage decomposition is observed for polyurethanes due to the combination of chemically different segments in the polymer chain. An initial weight-loss is observed for the ionomers due to their moisture-absorbing nature. Also an increase in the weight-

Fig. 1. TGA curves of castor oil based polyurethane anionomers.

loss is observed in the initial stages as the percentage of ionic content increases.

Differential scanning calorimetry was used to determine the phase transition occurring in the polyurethanes and values of glass transition temperature are presented in Table 1. The results show a shift in the T_g towards lower values as the ionic content increases. As the mole ratio of the ionic diol units is increased, the ionic content in the polymer as a whole increases. So the segmental compatibility between the hard and soft segments are reduced due to difference in the polarity. Thus the hard segments which were submerged in the soft segment tend to aggregate leading to more segmental purity of the basic polyol unit leading to phase separation.

Experimental

The ionic diol

was prepared by the reaction of maleic anhydride (1 mol) with 1,4-butanediol (2 mol) followed by addition across the unsaturated site using aqueous sodium bisulphite⁵. Castor oil was dried at 105° in vacuum for 4 h and the dried oil having a hydroxyl number of 164 was used.

Toluene diisocyanate (TDI) and dibutyltin dilaurate (Aldrich) were used as received. 1,4-Butanediol (BD) (Koch Labs) and dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) were separately distilled and stored over molecular sieves.

Synthesis of polyurethane anionomers : To castor oil (10 g), TDI (7.52 g, 0.432 mol) was added with stirring under N₂-atmosphere and the mixture was kept at 60° for 1 h. Then the temperature was raised to 90° and kept for 2 h. After the NCO content dropped to half the initial value (as determined by dibutylamine titration) the temperature was brought down to 60° and a mixture of the ionic diol (5.24 g, 0.0142 mol) and 1,4-butanediol (1.42 g, 0.0142 mol) in DMSO (50 ml) was added slowly with stirring followed by the catalyst dibutyltin dilaurate (0.01 g). After 1 h, DMSO (50 ml) was added to reduce the viscosity and the reaction was continued for 2 more h. Then the reaction mixture was poured in ten-fold excess of cold diethyl ether solution to

precipitate the polyurethane anionomer. By a similar procedure anionomer of another composition was also synthesised. The anionomers were dried at room temperature in vacuum and stored in a desiccator prior to characterisation.

The molecular weight analysis of the samples was determined using a Waters Associates gel permeation chromatograph equipped with a RI 410 detector. The solvent used was DMF stabilised with 0.01% LiBr with a flow rate of 1 ml/min. The columns used are μ -styragel of 10³, 10⁴, 10⁵ and 10⁶ Å pore size calibrated with polystyrene standards. FTIR were recorded as thin films over KBr disc using a Nicolet Impact 400 spectrometer. They were prepared by dissolving the purified samples in DMF, casting over a KBr disc and evaporation of the solvent at 60° in vacuum. Thermogravimetric analysis was carried out using a Du Pont 951 instrument and differential scanning calorimetric analysis on a Du Pont 910 instrument equipped with a standard cell at a heating rate of 10°/min under N₂-atmosphere. For the DSC analysis low temperature was achieved by quenching the samples in the cell using liquid nitrogen. The amount of samples taken for each run was 5 ± 0.2 mg.

References

1. D. DIETRICH, W. KEBERLE and H. WITT, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 1970, **1**, 40
2. S. RAMESH and G. RADHAKRISHNAN, *J. Macromol. Sci., Macromol. Rep.*, 1995, **A32**, 91; *J. Polym. Mat.*, 1995, **12**, 71
3. P. K. H. LAM, M. H. GEORGE and J. A. BARRIE, *Polym. Commun.*, 1989, **30**, 2321; 1991, **32**, 80; C. Z. YANG, T. G. GRASEL, J. L. BELL, R. A. REGISTER and S. L. COOPER, *J. Polym. Sci., Polym. Phys. Ed.*, 1991, **29**, 581; D. C. LEE, R. A. REGISTER, C. Z. YANG and S. L. COOPER, *Macromolecules*, 1988, **21**, 998; S. L. HSU, H. X. XIAO, H. H. SZMANT and K. C. FRISCH, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 1984, **29**, 2467; H. A. AL-SALAH, H. X. XIAO, J. A. MCLEAN, JR and K. C. FRISCH, *J. Polym. Sci., Polym. Chem. Ed.*, 1988, **26**, 1609; S. RAMESH and G. RADHAKRISHNAN, *Polymer*, 1994, **35**, 3107; *J. Macromol. Sci., Macromol. Rep.*, 1993, **A30**, 251.
4. P. RAJALINGAM and G. RADHAKRISHNAN, *Polym. Int.*, 1991, **25**, 87; J. H. SAUNDERS and K. C. FRISCH, "Polyurethanes : Chemistry & Technology", Interscience, New York, Vols. I (1962) and II (1964); N. NATCHIMUTHU, P. RAJALINGAM and G. RADHAKRISHNAN, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 1990, **41**, 3059; 1992, **44**, 981.
5. H. RAJAN, P. RAJALINGAM and G. RADHAKRISHNAN, *Polym. Commun.*, 1991, **32**, 93.